

A GIS-MCDM framework for the smart parcel locker site suitability analysis and optimizing urban last-mile delivery

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HIGHLIGHTS

- The multi-stage GIS-based Delphi-FAHP-TOPSIS methodology is introduced.
- The problem of smart parcel locker location selection is addressed.
- A novel perspective on optimizing urban last-mile delivery is offered.
- The real-life case study of Pardubice, Czech Republic is provided.
- Analytical insights for shaping the sustainable parcel delivery ecosystem are given.

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ABSTRACT

The surge in e-commerce has intensified the need for efficient urban last-mile delivery, with smart parcel lockers emerging as a sustainable solution. However, their optimal placement remains challenging due to spatial heterogeneity and decision uncertainty. This research proposes a five-stage methodology integrating Geographic Information Systems (GIS) with Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) to strategically site parcel lockers. The approach combines expert-driven criteria selection via Delphi method, Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process (FAHP) for criteria weighting while managing inherent judgmental ambiguity, GIS-based suitability mapping, and the Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) for ranking candidate sites. A case study in Pardubice, Czech Republic, validated the framework, recommending 50 new parcel locker sites. Sensitivity analysis highlighted road network accessibility, public transport proximity, and population density as critical criteria. By combining spatial analysis with structured decision-making, this study offers a reliable, transferable framework for optimizing parcel locker placement, enhancing last-mile delivery efficiency, and supporting sustainable urban logistics globally.

1. Introduction

Over the past decade, e-commerce has expanded at a compound annual growth rate exceeding 30%, reaching an estimated \$6 trillion in

2024 and projected to approach \$8 trillion by 2028 [1]. This rapid growth has imposed unprecedented stress on urban logistics and intensified last-mile delivery challenges [2]. Last-mile delivery – the final step in the supply chain from distribution hubs to consumers – contributes

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approximately 28% of total delivery costs [3], making it disproportionately expensive compared to other segments [4,5]. Moreover, it exacerbates traffic congestion and environmental pollution.

Smart parcel lockers (PLs) have emerged as a promising solution, offering secure, accessible locations where multiple parcels can be consolidated for customer pick-up or drop-off. Operating 24/7, these lockers eliminate failed delivery attempts and reduce route complexity, yielding up to 11% cost savings and a 2.5% reduction in CO₂ emissions [6,7]. By enhancing efficiency and sustainability in urban logistics, PLs help mitigate congestion and environmental impacts [8,9]. Their success, however, depends on strategic placement that accounts for local demand conditions, user accessibility, and operational constraints [10–12].

Reducing supply-chain emissions is a key challenge in urban logistics, and PLs can help lower last-mile impacts. Evidence from Norway indicates that shifting from home delivery to PL networks can reduce CO₂ emissions by 13%–32%, with emissions per parcel decreasing from about 187 g to 126–130 g when network optimization strategies are applied [13]. In China, Jiang et al. [14] reported that route-optimization strategies can reduce total costs and carbon emissions in last-mile delivery by 18.7%–51.2%, depending on implementation scale and operational parameters.

However, the environmental performance of PLs shows spatial variability: while integrating PLs in densely populated urban areas can achieve additional emission reductions of up to 5.4%, deployment in rural areas may increase emissions due to longer customer travel distances for collection [15].

From a lifecycle perspective, vehicle powertrain selection constitutes the primary determinant of overall environmental impact, with emissions ranging from 167 to 486 g CO₂e per package depending on vehicle type, while the contribution of automated delivery infrastructure remains modest at 2–6% [16]. These findings show that strategic PL placement, as addressed by our GIS-MCDM framework, helps maximize environmental benefits while accounting for spatial variations in population density and accessibility.

Selecting optimal sites for PLs requires a systematic, data-driven approach. Existing methods—ranging from optimization models [10] to multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) frameworks [17]—often assume spatial homogeneity and neglect conflicting criteria trade-offs (e.g., accessibility versus demand). Consequently, these approaches may identify locations that are optimal on a single metric but suboptimal in practice. Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and MCDM offer powerful, complementary tools: GIS enables spatial analysis and visualization, while MCDM structures the evaluation of multiple, conflicting criteria [18,19]. Despite widespread application in urban planning, the integration of GIS and MCDM for PL site selection remains underexplored.

1.1. Aim and contributions

This study addresses this gap by developing an integrated GIS–MCDM framework to identify optimal locations for PLs in urban environments based on 15 spatially-referenced criteria. The framework combines expert-driven criteria selection via the Delphi method, Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process (FAHP) for weighting criteria under uncertainty, GIS-based suitability mapping, Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) for ranking candidate sites, and sensitivity analysis to evaluate model robustness.

The contributions of this research are:

1. Integration of GIS with MCDM for PL site selection by combining FAHP for criteria weighting under uncertainty, GIS-based spatial analysis for continuous suitability mapping, and TOPSIS for ranking candidate sites.
2. Expert-validated criteria system through Delphi consultation with logistics academics and practitioners, establishing 15 criteria across three dimensions: accessibility, demand estimation, and infrastructure integration.

3. Spatial heterogeneity is considered by capturing continuous spatial variation in urban characteristics through GIS-based suitability surfaces, enabling identification of suitable areas across the entire urban landscape rather than evaluation of predefined discrete locations.
4. Comprehensive sensitivity analysis to assess model robustness by varying criteria weights and quantifying their impact on site rankings, identifying population density, public transport proximity, and road network accessibility as the most influential factors.

The framework is validated through a case study in Pardubice, Czech Republic, demonstrating its practical utility for urban logistics planning.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews relevant literature; Section 3 details the proposed methodology; Section 4 presents the case study results and discussion; and Section 5 concludes with insights, limitations and future work.

2. Literature review

The expansion of e-commerce has increased the demand for efficient last-mile delivery systems. Among the emerging solutions, smart PLs have gained strategic relevance due to their potential to reduce delivery costs and improve service accessibility. This section reviews three main areas of research: (i) Existing approaches used to identify suitable locations for PLs, (ii) GIS–MCDM integration for site-selection problems in urban transport and logistics, and (iii) GIS–MCDM applications in other domains (e.g., renewable energy and public-service/environmental management) to demonstrate the broader transferability of GIS–MCDM for spatial decision-making. This systematic review provides a comprehensive overview of current trends in PL siting methods and presents an integrated picture of how GIS–MCDM is used in related fields. We then identify the research gaps that this study addresses.

2.1. Methods for parcel locker site selection

Table 1 summarizes current methods for PL placement. Existing studies typically prioritize either optimization models or decision-maker preferences, while neglecting spatial factors in urban environments.

For instance, bi-level programming models by Yang et al. [20,21] balance economic efficiency and user satisfaction but lack detailed spatial data integration. Wang et al. [11] developed an optimization for demand uncertainty but omitted critical geographical variables affecting implementation.

MCDM methods have been used to handle multiple criteria and subjective judgments. Yalcin Kavus et al. [22] applied Bayesian Best Worst Method (B-BWM), with Pythagorean Fuzzy Weighted Aggregated Sum Product Assessment (PF-WASPAS), while Moslem and Pilla [17,23] employed Spherical Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process (SFAHP) to address decision uncertainty. These studies show structured decision-making but often neglect spatial context, focusing instead on trade-offs between criteria and treating the problem as a homogeneous space, which can lead to location recommendations that perform suboptimally under real-world spatial heterogeneity. Although Keeling et al. [24] considered accessibility metrics, most research lacks integration of spatial datasets within MCDM frameworks for comprehensive suitability analysis.

On the other hand, once PL locations are determined, designing their capacity becomes essential to meet the expected demand at each specific site and is formulated as an optimization problem that selects the number of compartments (available capacity) subject to the standard locker sizes and module configurations offered by operators. For instance, Mancini et al. [26] modeled demand and capacity uncertainty using stochastic programming with discrete scenarios, maximizing customer assignments under capacity constraints. Luo et al. [27] formulated a multi-objective network design problem and applied an Active-Learning Pareto Evolutionary Algorithm (ALPEA) to balance network cost and accessibility while accounting for capacity-driven

Table 1
Comparative analysis of methodologies in parcel locker location studies.

Study	Objective	Methodology	Location
Yang et al. [20] (2020)	Optimize the location of PLs by minimizing planners' cost and minimizing consumers' pick-up cost (equilibrium demand distribution).	Bi-level Programming Model, Bilevel Genetic Algorithm (BIGA).	Tianxin, China.
Keeling et al. [24] (2021)	Analyze the potential of public transportation facilities as hosts for common carrier PLs, focusing on accessibility and equity.	Multiple-criteria approach, Accessibility & Equity Metrics.	Portland, USA.
Lin et al. [25] (2022)	Study a profit-maximizing PL location problem under the Threshold Luce Model (TLM), considering competition from other delivery modes and customer choice.	Threshold Luce Model (TLM), Combinatorial Optimization Model, Integer Programs (IP), Conic Reformulation, Mixed-Integer Conic Quadratic Programming (MICQP).	(Numerical Experiments).
Wang et al. [11] (2022)	Propose an optimization model for location selection of PLs under uncertain demands, considering different parcel sizes.	Optimization Model, Integer Linear Programming (ILP).	(Numerical Experiments).
Yang et al. [21] (2023)	Maximize third-party PL supplier profit and maximize overall user satisfaction for location optimization.	Bilevel Programming Model, Genetic Algorithm (GA).	Shanghai, China.
Yalcin Kavus et al. [22] (2023)	Determine the most convenient location for the PLs, integrating probabilistic and fuzzy perspectives.	B-BWM, PF-WASPAS.	İstanbul, Turkey.
Zhang et al. [10] (2023)	Optimize the placement of PLs and parcel movements to minimize total cost in a hybrid crowd logistics network.	Mixed-Integer Linear Program (MILP), Binary Logit Model.	Toronto, Canada.
Moslem & Pilla [23] (2023)	Define the best location for PLs, incorporating decision-maker hesitancy.	SF-AHP.	Dublin, Ireland.
Moslem & Pilla [17] (2024)	Define the best location for PLs, addressing decision-maker uncertainty and vagueness.	SF-AHP, Euclidean Distance-Based Aggregation Method (EDBAM).	Dublin, Ireland.
Dayal & Unnikrishnan [12] (2025)	Maximize planner profit/minimize operational costs and maximize customer benefits/satisfaction for PL location and capacity.	Bi-level Optimization Model.	Mumbai, India.
Our Study	Optimize last mile delivery by determining the suitable areas to setting out PLs considering spatial analysis and decision-maker uncertainty.	FAHP, GIS, TOPSIS	Pardubice, Czechia.

Table 2
Comprehensive overview of GIS-MCDM-based site selection related to transportation studies.

Study	Objective	Weighting method	No. of Criteria	Ranking method	Location
Erbaş et al. [30]	Determining optimal sites for EVCS	FAHP	15	TOPSIS	Turkey
Kaya et al. [37]	Identifying optimal locations for EVCS	AHP	19	PROMETHEE-VIKOR	Turkey
Kaya et al. [31]	Determining places for EVCS	FAHP	25	TOPSIS	Turkey
Eren et al. [33]	Developed a hybrid methodology to select BSS sites in urban areas	AHP	21	VIKOR and Psychometric-VIKOR	Turkey
Bahadori et al. [34]	Identifying BSS sites	AHP	14	TOPSIS	Portugal
Kaya et al. [32]	Developed a methodology for EVCS site selection	FAHP	20	ELECTRE	Turkey.
Feng et al. [35]	Proposed an approach for emergency logistics centers site selection	Entropy-CRITIC	9	VIKOR	China.
Rane et al. [38]	Locating EVCS	MIF	13	TOPSIS	India
Elomiya et al. [36]	Identified a suitable locations to place off-site hydrogen stations in urban areas	FAHP	21	TOPSIS	Czechia

service performance. Sawik et al. [28] used multi-criteria simulation-optimization to study capacity utilization over time in large locker networks, while Rosca et al. [29] showed via agent-based and Monte Carlo simulation that customer behavior can strongly influence capacity requirements.

Overall, capacity design critically depends on selecting suitable PL locations that enable decision makers to estimate local demand accurately; therefore, our integrated GIS-MCDM framework supports not only robust site selection but also more reliable downstream capacity planning and resource allocation.

2.2. GIS-MCDM integration in site selection

Table 2 shows different GIS-MCDM applications across transportation planning related to infrastructure siting by combining GIS spatial analysis, considering weights of the criteria using subjective MCDM methods and ranking the alternatives using objective MCDM methods. For instance, Erbaş et al. [30] and Kaya et al. [31,32] used FAHP-TOPSIS for Electric Vehicle Charging Stations (EVCS), considering spatial and operational criteria. Similar integrations proved valuable for Bike-Sharing Systems (BSS) [33,34] and emergency logistics [35]. A recent study by Elomiya et al. [36] on hydrogen stations confirms the method's adaptability to urban contexts.

2.3. GIS-MCDM applications in other domains

GIS-MCDM is not only used in urban transport infrastructure planning but has also been widely adopted for site selection and suitability mapping in other domains, such as renewable energy and public-service/environmental management, as shown in Table 3.

In renewable energy, it has been used to identify suitable areas for Solar Photovoltaic (PV) and wind projects under competing technical, environmental, and socio-economic constraints. Rane et al. [39] used a GIS-based Multi-Influencing Factor (MIF) approach to delineate suitable zones for solar PV development in India. Almasad et al. [40] applied FAHP with PROMETHEE II to evaluate solar PV suitability in Saudi Arabia, while Demir et al. [41] proposed an Optimality-Based Site Growing (OBSG) approach for large-scale PV site selection in Turkey. Hosseini Dehshiri and Firoozabadi [42] extended solar siting by incorporating hydrogen storage considerations using Step-wise Weight Assessment Ratio Analysis (SWARA) in Iran. For wind and marine renewables, Gil-Garcia et al. [43] assessed offshore wind locations in the USA using AHP and TOPSIS, and Shao et al. [44] developed a framework for tidal current power plant site selection in China using FAHP-CRITIC and VIKOR.

GIS-MCDM has also been applied to public-service and environmental-management decisions. Nyimbili et al. [45] integrated

Table 3
Comprehensive overview of GIS-MCDM-based site selection studies.

Study	Objective	Weighting method	Criteria	Ranking method	Location
Nyimbili et al. [45]	Identified optimal sites for new fire stations	FAHP	6	BWM	Turkey
Gil-García et al. [43]	Developed an approach for optimal offshore wind location assessment	AHP	15	TOPSIS	USA
Albraheem et al. [47]	Conducted a wind farm site suitability analysis	AHP	9	AHP	Saudi Arabia
Almasad et al. [40]	Developed a site suitability model for solar PV power projects	FAHP	12	PROMETHEE II	Saudi Arabia
Demir et al. [41]	Developed a methodology for selecting large-scale PV plant sites	AHP	6	OBSG	Turkey
Hosseini Dehshiri & Firoozabadi [42]	Introduced a framework for identifying suitable areas for solar power plants with hydrogen storage systems	SWARA	9	SWARA	Iran
Raza et al. [48]	Proposed a comprehensive framework for site suitability for utility-scale solar PV and wind energy projects	AHP	9	AHP	Pakistan
Shao et al. [44]	Developed a three-stage decision framework for tidal current power plant site selection	FAHP-CRITIC	9	VIKOR	China
Zewdie et al. [46]	Identified suitable waste disposal sites	AHP	10	AHP	Ethiopia
Rane et al. [39]	Identified optimal sites for solar photovoltaic power plants using multi-influencing factor technique	MIF	9	-	India

FAHP with BWM to support fire-station site selection in Turkey, and Zewdie et al. [46] used AHP-based GIS analysis to identify suitable waste disposal sites in Ethiopia.

Overall, these studies highlight the importance of GIS-MCDM integration across sectors and underline its relevance for complex urban siting tasks, where criteria trade-offs and spatial variability must be handled systematically.

2.4. Research gap and motivation

This research is motivated by the growing challenges in urban last-mile delivery driven by the expansion of e-commerce. With global e-commerce sales projected to reach \$8 trillion by 2028 and last-mile delivery accounting for approximately 28% of total logistics costs [1,3], the strategic placement of smart PLs has become a critical priority for logistics operators, urban planners, and policymakers. PLs can reduce delivery costs by up to 51%, decrease carbon emissions by 13–32%, and eliminate failed delivery attempts [13,14].

However, their effectiveness depends on optimal site selection. Inadequately located PLs may remain underutilized, fail to capture sufficient demand, or increase environmental impacts if customers must travel excessive distances for collection [15].

As our literature review reveals, existing approaches to PL placement rely on optimization models or standalone MCDM methods that

conceptualize urban space as homogeneous, neglecting the spatial heterogeneity that characterizes real urban environments (Table 1). Conversely, GIS-MCDM integration has proven effective for urban transport infrastructure problems (Table 2) and other domains such as renewable-energy siting and public-service planning (Table 3), yet this methodological framework remains notably underutilized for PL placement.

Consequently, this methodological gap leads to three key limitations: (1) insufficient spatial data incorporation, (2) inadequate handling of urban complexity, and (3) a lack of frameworks that combine spatial analysis with decision uncertainty management.

Our study addresses these gaps by developing a GIS-MCDM framework that integrates FAHP for criteria weighting under uncertainty, GIS for spatial suitability analysis, and TOPSIS for ranking the proposed alternatives.

3. Methodology

This study employs a five-stage methodology, illustrated in Fig. 1, to develop a suitability map for siting smart PLs. The process integrates quantitative analyses and qualitative assessments to establish a structured approach for identifying appropriate locations. The overall goal is to evaluate potential areas based on relevant criteria, ultimately highlighting the most suitable sites for locker placement.

Fig. 1. The proposed methodology.

3.1. Stage 1: criteria determination

In the first stage of the proposed methodology we focus on establishing the foundational criteria and sub-criteria that govern the suitability assessment for PL placement. The process began by compiling a preliminary list of criteria drawn from existing literature and the opinions of the authors. To ensure these criteria were comprehensive and practically relevant, the Delphi method [49] was utilized, engaging a panel of six experts. This panel comprised two academic professors specializing in spatial analysis and logistics, along with four industry professionals from Czech parcel delivery companies (DPD, GLS, Czech Post, and AlzaBox). Through sequential, anonymized rounds of questionnaires facilitated by a summary of collective feedback after each round, the Delphi technique guided the experts toward consensus, resulting in a refined set of primary criteria and associated sub-criteria that formed the basis for the subsequent analysis.

3.2. Stage 2: criteria weights

The criteria-weighting stage employs FAHP to quantify the importance of the sub-criteria while addressing the uncertainty in expert judgments through Triangular Fuzzy Numbers (TFNs). The experts conducted pairwise comparisons among the sub-criteria using the linguistic scale provided in Table 4. These comparisons yielded an $n \times n$ fuzzy pairwise-comparison matrix A , as shown in Eq. (1).

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} (1, 1, 1) & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ \frac{1}{a_{12}} & (1, 1, 1) & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{1}{a_{1n}} & \frac{1}{a_{2n}} & \dots & (1, 1, 1) \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

The elements within this matrix, represented by a_{ij} , are TFNs characterized by a triplet format (l, m, u) , where l , m , and u represent the lower, middle, and upper values, respectively.

To ensure logical coherence in the judgments is crucial; therefore, the consistency of the pairwise comparison matrix was evaluated [32,40,50]. This involved calculating the Consistency Ratio (CR), determined using Eq. (2):

$$CR = \frac{CI}{RI} \quad (2)$$

where CI represents the Consistency Index, calculated according to Eq. (3):

$$CI = \frac{\lambda_{max} - n}{n - 1} \quad (3)$$

Where, λ_{max} represents the largest eigenvalue of the pairwise comparison matrix, and n is the size of the matrix. The term RI stands for the

Table 4
Linguistic variables and their TFNs [40].

Linguistic variables	TFNs	Reciprocal TFNs
Equal	(1, 1, 1)	(1, 1, 1)
Moderate	(2, 3, 4)	(1/4, 1/3, 1/2)
Strong	(4, 5, 6)	(1/6, 1/5, 1/4)
Very strong	(6, 7, 8)	(1/8, 1/7, 1/6)
Extremely strong	(9, 9, 9)	(1/9, 1/9, 1/9)
Intermediate values between the above scale scores:	(1, 2, 3), (3, 4, 5), (5, 6, 7), (7, 8, 9)	(1/3, 1/2, 1), (1/5, 1/4, 1/3), (1/7, 1/6, 1/5), (1/9, 1/8, 1/7)

Random Index, which provides a measure of consistency expected from a randomly generated matrix of size $n \times n$. The standard RI values, derived by Saaty [51], are presented in Table 5.

The pairwise comparison matrix is considered consistent if $CR \leq 0.1$; otherwise the expert judgments require re-evaluation.

Once the consistency of individual expert matrices was consistent, their judgments were aggregated to form a single, representative fuzzy pairwise comparison matrix. Considering n experts and x evaluation criteria, where $\tilde{F}_{ij}^{(k)}$ represents the TFN comparison of criterion F_i over F_j by the k -th expert, the consolidated judgment $\tilde{F}_{ij} = (l_{ij}, m_{ij}, u_{ij})$ is obtained using the geometric mean method proposed by Liu et al. [52], as shown in Eq. (4):

$$\tilde{F}_{ij} = (l_{ij}, m_{ij}, u_{ij}) = \left(\prod_{k=1}^n \tilde{F}_{ij}^{(k)} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} = \left(\tilde{F}_{ij}^{(1)} \otimes \tilde{F}_{ij}^{(2)} \otimes \dots \otimes \tilde{F}_{ij}^{(n)} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \\ = \left[\left(\prod_{k=1}^n l_{ij}^{(k)} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}}, \left(\prod_{k=1}^n m_{ij}^{(k)} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}}, \left(\prod_{k=1}^n u_{ij}^{(k)} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \right] \quad (4)$$

Subsequently, the fuzzy weights (\tilde{W}_i) for each criterion were derived by first calculating the fuzzy geometric mean (\tilde{F}_i) for each row of the aggregated matrix using Eq. (5), and then normalizing these values as described in Eq. (6), following the approach detailed by Torfi et al. [53]:

$$\tilde{F}_i = (\tilde{F}_{i1} \otimes \tilde{F}_{i2} \otimes \dots \otimes \tilde{F}_{ix})^{\frac{1}{x}} \quad (5)$$

$$\tilde{W}_i = \frac{\tilde{F}_i}{\sum_{j=1}^x \tilde{F}_j} \quad (6)$$

To obtain crisp, actionable weights from the TFNs $\tilde{W}_i = (l, m, u)$, the center of area (CoA) defuzzification method was utilized, as defined in Eq. (7):

$$W^* = \frac{l + m + u}{3} \quad (7)$$

Finally, the resulting crisp weights (W^*) were normalized to ensure that their sum equals one.

3.3. Stage 3: final suitability map

This stage focuses on leveraging GIS for geospatial visualization and the creation of the final suitability map, which identifies optimal sites for PLs based on the criteria and weights established in previous stages. The process begins with gathering the necessary geospatial data corresponding to each criterion, typically in standard GIS formats such as shapefiles or raster layers.

GIS enables the integration, management, analysis, and visualization of multiple layers of geographic information [54,55]. By supporting both vector and raster data, it facilitates comprehensive spatial analysis and effective communication of results. GIS processing workflow involves the following key steps:

- 1. Normalization:** Geographic data layers for each criterion are normalized. This transforms data values, irrespective of their original units or ranges, to a common scale (typically between 0 and 1), ensuring consistency across datasets and enabling direct comparison for integration.

Table 5
Random index table [51].

n	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
RI	0.00	0.00	0.52	0.89	1.11	1.25	1.35	1.40	1.45	1.49	1.51	1.54	1.56	1.57	1.58

- 2. **Reclassification:** Following normalization, the data layers are reclassified by assigning new values to the normalized data, often grouping ranges into categories (e.g., ‘high’, ‘medium’, ‘low’ suitability). Reclassification simplifies the interpretation of complex data layers and prepares them for the final suitability assessment.
- 3. **Spatial Analysis:** GIS-based spatial analysis techniques are applied to integrate the processed layers and identify spatial patterns, relationships, and trends relevant to PL suitability [56,57]. Techniques such as calculating Euclidean distance, which measures the straight-line distance between geographic features [54], are instrumental in evaluating proximity-based criteria within this spatial context. These analyses help in understanding the spatial distribution of suitability based on the combined influence of all criteria.

The primary outcome of this stage is the final suitability map, visually representing the areas most suitable for the placement of PLs according to the defined model and processed geospatial data.

3.4. Stage 4: proposed new locations

In this stage, potential new locations for PLs are identified and subsequently ranked based on their suitability. The primary input for this stage is the final suitability map generated in Stage 3, along with specific suitability values extracted for each proposed new location corresponding to the normalized criteria layers. In this stage TOPSIS, developed by Hwang and Yoon [58], is employed to perform this ranking. Its core principle involves ranking alternatives by measuring their simultaneous proximity to an ideal best solution (Positive Ideal Solution, PIS) and distance from an ideal worst solution (Negative Ideal Solution, NIS) [43,59]. The alternative closest to the PIS and farthest from the NIS is considered the optimal choice. The detailed steps of TOPSIS method are as follows:

- 1. **Decision Matrix Formation:** A decision matrix, Z , is constructed using the performance values of the proposed locations (alternatives) against the evaluation criteria. The matrix is structured as shown in Eq. (8):

$$Z = (z_{pq})_{s \times t} : \begin{matrix} & C_1 & C_2 & \dots & C_t \\ A_1 & z_{11} & z_{12} & \dots & z_{1t} \\ A_2 & z_{21} & z_{22} & \dots & z_{2t} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ A_s & z_{s1} & z_{s2} & \dots & z_{st} \end{matrix} \quad (8)$$

Here, z_{pq} represents the performance value (or extracted suitability value) of the p -th alternative (A_p , where $p = 1, 2, \dots, s$) with respect to the q -th criterion (C_q , where $q = 1, 2, \dots, t$). Let y_{pq} denote the initial performance value before normalization.

- 2. **Normalization of Decision Matrix:** The decision matrix is normalized to eliminate scale differences between criteria and ensure comparability. Vector normalization is applied using Eq. (9):

$$z_{pq} = \frac{y_{pq}}{\sqrt{\sum_{p=1}^s y_{pq}^2}}, \quad \text{for } p = 1, 2, \dots, s; \quad q = 1, 2, \dots, t \quad (9)$$

- 3. **Weighted Normalization:** The normalized values z_{pq} are then weighted according to the criteria importance derived in Stage 2. The weighted normalized value w_{pq} is calculated by multiplying the normalized value z_{pq} by the corresponding criterion weight b_q , as shown in Eq. (10):

$$w_{pq} = b_q \times z_{pq} \quad (10)$$

- 4. **Establishing PIS and NIS:** The Positive Ideal Solution (PIS) and Negative Ideal Solution (NIS) are determined from the weighted normalized matrix by selecting the best and worst values across all alternatives. Accordingly, B^+ represents the most preferable value for each criterion and B^- represents the least preferable value. The PIS and NIS are defined as vectors as shown in Eqs. (11) and (12):

$$B^+ = [w_1^+, w_2^+, \dots, w_t^+] \quad (11)$$

$$B^- = [w_1^-, w_2^-, \dots, w_t^-] \quad (12)$$

Here, w_q^+ and w_q^- denote the PIS and NIS components for criterion q (i.e., w_1^+, \dots, w_t^+ and w_1^-, \dots, w_t^- are the entries of B^+ and B^- , respectively). The definitions of w_q^+ and w_q^- depend on whether a criterion is beneficial (higher values are better) or non-beneficial (lower values are better).

For beneficial criteria:

$$w_q^+ = \max_p \{w_{pq}\} \quad (13)$$

$$w_q^- = \min_p \{w_{pq}\} \quad (14)$$

For non-beneficial criteria:

$$w_q^+ = \min_p \{w_{pq}\} \quad (15)$$

$$w_q^- = \max_p \{w_{pq}\} \quad (16)$$

- 5. **Determine Separation from PIS and NIS:** The distance of each alternative from the PIS (D_p^+) and NIS (D_p^-) is calculated using the Euclidean distance metric, summed across all criteria as shown in Eqs. (17) and (18):

$$D_p^+ = \sum_{q=1}^t |w_{pq} - w_q^+| \quad (17)$$

$$D_p^- = \sum_{q=1}^t |w_{pq} - w_q^-| \quad (18)$$

- 6. **Computing Relative Closeness to PIS:** The relative closeness (RC_p^+) of each alternative p to the ideal solution is calculated using Eq. (19) ranging from 0 to 1.

$$RC_p^+ = \frac{D_p^-}{D_p^+ + D_p^-} \quad (19)$$

A higher RC_p^+ value indicates a better performance, meaning the alternative is closer to the PIS and farther from the NIS. Finally, the alternatives (proposed locations) are ranked in descending order based on their RC_p^+ values.

The output of this stage is a ranked list of the proposed new locations, providing a clear recommendation based on the TOPSIS evaluation.

3.5. Stage 5: sensitivity analysis

The final stage assesses the robustness and reliability of the location rankings derived from the TOPSIS analysis in Stage 4. To achieve this, a sensitivity analysis is conducted [32,33,44]. This involves systematically varying the criteria weights determined in Stage 2 to observe the impact of these changes on the final ranking of the proposed locations.

For each sub-criterion j at a given perturbation level p , the individual sensitivity $\sigma_j^{(p)}$ is calculated as the percentage of candidate sites

whose rankings change compared to the baseline scenario, as shown in Eq. (20):

$$\sigma_j^{(p)} = \frac{N_j^{(p)}}{N} \times 100\% \quad (20)$$

where $N_j^{(p)}$ is the number of sites that experience ranking changes when criterion j is perturbed by $\pm p\%$, and N is the total number of candidate sites.

To provide an aggregate measure of model responsiveness at each perturbation level, the overall sensitivity index $S^{(p)}$ is computed as the normalized sum of individual sensitivities across all n sub-criteria, as computed in Eq. (21):

$$S^{(p)} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{\sigma_j^{(p)}}{100} \quad (21)$$

where n represents the total number of sub-criteria (in this study, $n = 15$). The sensitivity index $S^{(p)}$ ranges from 0 to 1, where values closer to 0 indicate high model stability (few ranking changes), and values closer to 1 indicate high sensitivity (substantial ranking changes across criteria).

By evaluating the stability of the results across a range of scenarios, this analysis provides insights into the resilience of the recommended sites to uncertainty and shifts in decision-maker priorities, thereby supporting the reliability of the proposed location choices.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Study area

Our study focuses on the Pardubice District within the Pardubický region of the Czech Republic as shown in Fig. 2. Located at approximately 50.03° N and 15.78° E, the district spans about 880 km² and had a population of about 180,000 as of 31 December 2024 [60].

The reason for choosing Pardubice to implement our framework is influenced by recent changes in postal services. Czech Post closed 300 branches nationwide by July 1, 2023, which reduced its locations in Pardubice from 13 to 7 [61]. This reduction increases reliance on alternative delivery methods like PLs. Currently, several companies operate lockers in the area, including Alza Box, PPL Parcel Box, Pilulka Box, DHL Locker, DPD, Balíkovna Box, Zásilkovna (Z-Box), GLS, and OX Points as shown in Fig. 3. Given the growing e-commerce demand and

Fig. 2. Study area.

Fig. 3. Distribution of existing parcel lockers in Pardubice.

reduced postal infrastructure, the existing PL network might face capacity challenges, motivating the search for optimal new locations, so our framework will help these companies expand their networks.

4.2. Application of stage 1: criteria determination

The criteria for selecting optimal PL locations were initially drawn from existing literature and refined through expert consultation as explained in Section 3.1.

Multiple rounds of structured feedback led to a consensus on 3 main criteria and 15 sub-criteria as follows:

- **Accessibility (C1):** Factors influencing ease of user access, including road networks, public transport proximity, cycling path availability, and parking.
- **Demand estimation (C2):** Indicators of potential usage, such as population density, proximity to commercial and residential areas, university campuses, and the distribution of existing lockers.
- **Infrastructure and facilities (C3):** Integration with existing urban amenities that attract footfall, like ATMs, EVCS, schools, post offices, petrol stations, and shopping centers.

These categories and their corresponding sub-criteria are shown in Table 6 with supporting literature for each sub-criterion used.

4.3. Application of stage 2: criteria weights

In this stage, weights were assigned to the main criteria and their respective sub-criteria using FAHP to quantify their relative importance for smart PL placement suitability. A Python script was employed to implement the FAHP calculations, generating the weights detailed in Table A.1 (Appendix A).

The FAHP assigned weights of 0.3789 to Accessibility (C1), 0.3147 to Demand Estimation (C2), and 0.3064 to Infrastructure and Facilities (C3). Subsequently, FAHP was applied individually within each main category to determine the local weights for its associated sub-criteria. The final (global) weight for each sub-criterion was then computed by multiplying its local weight by the weight of its parent main criterion.

The consistency of the pairwise comparisons was verified by calculating *CR* for each comparison matrix. As shown in Table A.1, all calculated *CR* values were well below the acceptable threshold of 0.1, indicating a satisfactory level of consistency in the expert judgments used for weighting.

4.4. Application of stage 3: final suitability map

This stage involved processing geospatial data for the 15 sub-criteria to generate the final suitability map. Data sources are detailed in Table 7. Initially, the study area boundaries were defined, and all data layers

Table 6
Criteria and sub-criteria for assessing parcel locker suitability.

Main Criteria	Sub-criteria	Explanation	Literature source
C1. Accessibility	C1.1. Roads Network	Well-connected road infrastructure allows customers to reach locker locations by their car, particularly important for bulky or heavy parcels	Kavus et al. [22], Moslem & Pilla [23]
	C1.2. Main public transport stations	Lockers near bus stops, tram stations, or train terminals serve commuters who can collect packages during their daily journeys without detours	Terh & Cao [62], Schaefer et al. [63]
	C1.3. Cycling paths	With growing urban cycling culture, lockers along bike routes attract environmentally users and reduce car dependency for last-mile delivery	Terh & Cao [62], Eren et al. [33]
	C1.4. Parking areas	Short-term parking nearby is practical for drivers who need a quick stop to retrieve their items without illegal parking	Kaya et al. [37], Moslem and Pilla [23]
C2. Demand estimation	C2.1. Populations	Densely populated neighborhoods generate higher parcel volumes, as more residents translate to greater demand for delivery services	Kaya et al. [37], Schaefer et al. [63], Eren et al. [33]
	C2.2. Business buildings	Commercial zones have high deliveries of supplies, documents, and orders throughout the workweek	Eren et al. [33], Kavus et al. [22]
	C2.3. Residential areas	Households represent the core user base, especially in areas with high e-commerce adoption and limited home delivery options during work hours	Kaya et al. [37], Kavus et al. [22]
	C2.4. University campus	Students and academic staff frequently order textbooks, electronics, and everyday items online, creating concentrated demand within campus boundaries	Terh & Cao [62], Eren et al. [33]
	C2.5. Existing parcel lockers	Mapping current locker locations helps identify underserved areas and prevents clustering that would leave some neighborhoods without coverage	Kavus et al. [22]
C3. Infrastructure and facilities	C3.1. Automated teller machines (ATMs)	ATM locations already draw regular foot traffic for banking errands, offering a natural opportunity to combine financial and parcel tasks in one trip	Yildiz et al. [64]
	C3.2. Electric vehicle charging stations	Users, during the waiting time for charging their electric cars, could use the opportunity to collect or send their parcels, making it a dual-purpose trip	Kaya et al. [37]
	C3.3. Schools	Morning drop-offs and afternoon pick-ups bring parents to school gates twice daily, fitting parcel collection into existing routines	Terh & Cao [62]
	C3.4. Post offices	Traditional postal customers are already familiar with parcel services, and co-location can extend service hours beyond post office operating times	Moslem and Pilla [23]
	C3.5. Petrol stations	People filling up their vehicles could use the opportunity to collect or dispatch parcels	Kaya et al. [37]
	C3.6. Shop centers	Shopping hubs attract crowds, making them ideal for placing parcel boxes	Eren et al. [33], Kavus et al. [22]

Table 7
Criteria data types, and their sources.

Criteria	Format of data	Geodetic coordinate system	Source
C1.1	Vector	WGS84	https://data.nextgis.com/en/region/CZ-53/base
C1.2	Vector	S-JTSK - Krovak East North -EPSG:5514	https://www.dpmp.cz/terminaly-hd/terminal-mhd.html
C1.3	Vector	S-JTSK - Krovak East North -EPSG:5514	https://www.pardubickykraj.cz/vrstvy-ve-formatu-shp
C1.4	Vector	WGS84	https://data.nextgis.com/en/region/CZ-53/base
C2.1	Raster	S-JTSK - Krovak East North -EPSG:5514	https://geoportal.cuzk.cz/
C2.2	Vector	S-JTSK - Krovak East North -EPSG:5514	https://geoportal.cuzk.cz/
C2.3	Vector	WGS84	https://data.nextgis.com/en/region/CZ-53/base
C2.4	Vector	WGS84	https://data.nextgis.com/en/region/CZ-53/base
C2.5	Vector	S-JTSK - Krovak East North -EPSG:5514	https://www.balikovna.cz/cs/uvod https://gls-group.com/CZ/en/home/ https://pickup.dpd.cz/ https://www.zasilkovna.cz/zbox https://www.dhl-servicepoint.cz/dhl-locker/ https://www.alzabox.cz/ https://www.ppl.cz/poslat-zasilku https://www.pilulka.cz/pilulka-box https://www.oxpointbox.cz/
C3.1	Vector	WGS84	https://data.nextgis.com/en/region/CZ-53/base
C3.2	Vector	S-JTSK - Krovak East North -EPSG:5514	https://www.cistadoprava.cz/stanice-ceska-republika/
C3.3	Vector	WGS84	https://data.nextgis.com/en/region/CZ-53/base
C3.4	Vector	WGS84	https://data.nextgis.com/en/region/CZ-53/base
C3.5	Vector	WGS84	https://data.nextgis.com/en/region/CZ-53/base
C3.6	Vector	WGS84	https://data.nextgis.com/en/region/CZ-53/base

were standardized to the S-JTSK Krovak East North coordinate system (EPSG:5514), the official geodetic reference system for the Czech Republic, ensuring spatial consistency across datasets from various origins.

Following data preparation, appropriate spatial analyses were performed for each criterion layer using ArcGIS Pro (3.5.4). For instance, Euclidean distance analysis was applied to generate continuous proximity surfaces, measuring the straight line distance from each 20m × 20m raster cell to the nearest feature of interest (e.g., nearest road, public transport station, or shopping center). Subsequently, all spatial layers were normalized, converting pixel values to a common 0–1 scale for comparability. Fig. 4 displays the resulting normalized maps, where white color indicates higher suitability for criteria C1.4, C2.1, C2.4, C2.5, C3.1, C3.2, C3.3, C3.4, C3.5, while black indicates higher suitability for C1.1, C1.2, C1.3, C2.2, C2.3, C3.6. These normalized layers were then reclassified using the Jenks natural breaks method [65] into nine suitability classes (1 = least suitable, 9 = most suitable) with a pixel resolution of 20m × 20m as illustrated in Fig. B.1, in Appendix B.

The final suitability map was produced by integrating the 15 reclassified sub-criteria layers through a weighted overlay analysis. The weights used in this step were those derived from the FAHP analysis in Stage 2

as shown in Table A.1. This process yielded the final suitability map for smart PL placement in Pardubice, depicted in Fig. 5.

Table 8 provides a summary of the final suitability map, showing the suitability index range, area coverage (km² and percentage), for each of the nine suitability classes.

4.5. Application of stage 4: proposed new locations

In the process of evaluating suitable sites for smart PLs in Pardubice, a total of 50 sites were identified based on the categories ranging from suitable to very highly suitable. The determination of 50 locations was influenced by the existing number of PLs within the city. Collaborative discussions with the Pardubice municipality ensured that the selected locations would create a consistent and evenly distributed service network across the city. Fig. 6 provides a visual representation of these proposed sites alongside existing PLs.

To rank the proposed PLs locations TOPSIS method has been executed using the Python code. In this method, the cost/benefit aspects of the criteria were initially defined. While all the sub-criteria were considered beneficial, C2.5 was the only criterion regarded as cost-centric. After this step, a decision matrix was generated using the performance values derived from GIS assessments. A standard decision matrix emerged from the normalization of these values. Furthermore, a weighted standard decision matrix was achieved by multiplying the normalized values with the respective criterion weights.

By assessing the relative closeness to PIS for each location and organizing these values from highest to lowest, the ranking of the 50 potential PL sites was visualized in Fig. 7.

Table 9 details the top 10 highest-ranked locations, presenting their specific PIS/NIS distances and relative closeness scores. The analysis identified location ‘P14’ as the most suitable according to the TOPSIS evaluation, while ‘P22’ ranked lowest among the 50 proposed sites.

4.6. Application of stage 5: sensitivity analysis

A sensitivity analysis was performed to evaluate the robustness of site rankings by systematically varying sub-criteria weights. The analysis generated 150 scenarios by perturbing each of the 15 sub-criteria weights by ±10%, ±20%, ±30%, ±40%, and ±50%, with subsequent weight re-normalization to maintain the constraint $\sum w_j = 1$.

For each scenario, the individual sensitivity $\sigma_j^{(p)}$ was calculated using Eq. (20), where $N = 50$ candidate sites were re-ranked using TOPSIS after each weight perturbation. The overall sensitivity index $S^{(p)}$ was then computed according to Eq. (21) to quantify the aggregate model responsiveness at each perturbation level.

Fig. 8 presents the sensitivity analysis results as radar charts for each perturbation level. Each chart displays the individual sensitivity values $\sigma_j^{(p)}$ for all 15 sub-criteria, with the corresponding overall sensitivity index $S^{(p)}$ annotated in the upper-right corner of each subplot.

The radar charts reveal distinctive sensitivity profiles across perturbation levels. At ±10% perturbation ($S^{(10)} = 0.311$), the sensitivity pattern exhibits pronounced peaks at C2.1 (Population Density) and C1.2 (Public Transport), while infrastructure criteria (C3.1–C3.5) form a relatively flat region near the center, indicating limited influence on ranking stability. As perturbation magnitude increases, the overall sensitivity index grows progressively: $S^{(20)} = 0.426$, $S^{(30)} = 0.486$, $S^{(40)} = 0.539$, and $S^{(50)} = 0.576$. This monotonic increase reflects the expected behavior that larger weight modifications induce more substantial changes in site rankings.

Notably, the shape of the sensitivity profile remains consistent across perturbation levels, indicating that the relative importance hierarchy among criteria is preserved regardless of perturbation magnitude. The criteria C2.1 (Population Density), C1.2 (Public Transport), C1.1 (Roads

Fig. 4. Normalized maps for the criteria used.

Fig. 5. Suggested suitability map for smart parcel lockers in Pardubice.

Table 8
Suitability index and corresponding area for each class.

Class	Site suitability	Area (km ²)	Area (%)	Class suitability index range
1	Extremely Low	66.01	7.15	2.398 - 3.795
2	Very Low	102.40	11.10	3.796 - 4.571
3	Low	110.87	12.01	4.572 - 5.348
4	Low to Moderate	108.77	11.79	5.349 - 6.124
5	Moderate	129.97	14.08	6.125 - 6.931
6	Moderate to High	133.69	14.49	6.932 - 7.707
7	High	114.37	12.39	7.708 - 8.515
8	Very High	85.67	9.28	8.516 - 9.415
9	Extremely High	71.02	7.70	9.416 - 10.320

Network), and C3.6 (Shop Centers) consistently exhibit the highest individual sensitivities, confirming their dominant influence on site suitability rankings. Conversely, criteria such as C3.1 (ATMs), C3.4 (Post Offices), and C2.5 (Existing Lockers) demonstrate low sensitivity values even at $\pm 50\%$ perturbation, suggesting that the model is robust to variations in these factors.

The maximum sensitivity index observed ($S^{(50)} = 0.576$) indicates that even under extreme weight perturbations, approximately 42% of the ranking structure remains stable, demonstrating acceptable robustness of the proposed GIS-MCDM framework for PL site selection.

Fig. 6. Existing and potential parcel locker locations.

Fig. 7. TOPSIS ranking of potential parcel locker locations.

Table 9
Ranking of top 10 potential parcel lockers by TOPSIS.

Rank	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Parcel locker	P14	P44	P15	P41	P39	P19	P49	P3	P2	P5
PIS	0.0505	0.0557	0.0515	0.0561	0.0601	0.0610	0.0622	0.0579	0.0618	0.0721
NIS	0.0525	0.0558	0.0489	0.0473	0.0494	0.0497	0.0461	0.0422	0.0445	0.0503
Relative closeness	0.5097	0.5004	0.4871	0.4574	0.4511	0.4490	0.4257	0.4216	0.4186	0.4109

Fig. 8. Sensitivity analysis radar charts for each perturbation level. The radial axis represents the percentage of sites with ranking changes ($\sigma_j^{(p)}$). The overall sensitivity index $S^{(p)}$ is shown for each perturbation level.

5. Conclusions, limitations, and future work

This study presents an integrated GIS–MCDM framework to optimize the placement of smart PLs in urban environments, addressing a pressing challenge in last-mile delivery logistics. We developed a comprehensive approach to site selection through a structured five-stage methodology, beginning with criteria determination via the Delphi method, weighting with FAHP, GIS-based suitability mapping, location ranking using TOPSIS, and sensitivity analysis. Applied to Pardubice, Czech Republic, the framework identified and ranked 50 potential locker locations, with site P14 emerging as the most suitable. Sensitivity analysis further revealed that road networks (C1.1), public transport access (C1.2), and population density (C2.1) exert significant influence on the suitability rankings, underscoring their critical role in urban logistics planning.

Theoretically, this research contributes to the field of urban logistics by illustrating the efficacy of combining GIS and MCDM to tackle complex spatial decision-making problems. By incorporating spatial data into a multi-criteria framework where previous approaches often treated urban spaces as homogeneous or prioritized single optimization metrics over comprehensive analysis. The identification of 15 criteria across accessibility, demand estimation, and infrastructure categories, refined through expert consensus, provides a robust foundation for understanding the multifaceted factors that govern PL placement.

Practically, the framework offers a replicable tool for logistics operators and urban planners to enhance the efficiency of last-mile delivery systems. In Pardubice, the proposed locations address the strain on existing postal infrastructure following the closure of Czech Post branches, aligning with the growing demand driven by e-commerce.

By prioritizing accessibility and demand, the methodology supports reduced delivery times, lower operational costs, and improved service accessibility.

Nevertheless, the framework is limited by its reliance on static criteria and fixed weights, which may not fully capture temporal changes such as evolving population patterns, traffic flows, or infrastructure modifications. In addition, this study focuses on a single medium-sized city (Pardubice), which limits our ability to assess the framework’s performance across diverse urban typologies.

Future research should develop a dynamic digital twin model to overcome these limitations. This enhancement could enable real time integration of urban dynamics and operational factors, including installation and rental costs, land ownership constraints, locker capacity optimization, enhanced security metrics beyond spatial proximity, and detailed routing efficiency; it could also support explicit incorporation of economic considerations by creating spatial cost surfaces based on land value indices, zoning regulations, and infrastructure availability, and by developing multi stage decision frameworks in which spatial suitability screening is followed by detailed cost–benefit analysis. Comparative applications of the proposed GIS–MCDM methodology should also be conducted across different urban scales, including megacities with complex, high density urban forms and extensive transportation networks, as well as small towns characterized by lower population densities and simpler infrastructure configurations. Such studies would provide valuable insights into how the relative importance of criteria shifts across contexts, which criteria become more or less relevant at different scales, and how the framework’s recommendations perform under varying levels of urban complexity. These advancements will further refine the

model's practical applicability and strengthen its value in adaptive urban logistics planning.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Akram Elomiya: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jiří Křupka:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Vladimir Simic:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Resources, Project administration, Formal analysis. **Libor Švadlenka:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Stefan Jovčić:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Dragan Pamucar:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft.

Appendix A. Criteria weights by FAHP

Table A.1
Weights of the criteria by FAHP.

Main criteria	Main criteria weights	Sub-criteria	Sub-criteria weights	Final sub-criteria weights
C1	0.3789	C1.1	0.2762	0.1047
		C1.2	0.2762	0.1047
		C1.3	0.2356	0.0893
		C1.4	0.2119	0.0803
		Check consistency for C1.1, C1.2, C1.3, and C1.4		
		CR		0.0579
C2	0.3147	C2.1	0.2754	0.0867
		C2.2	0.1952	0.0614
		C2.3	0.1871	0.0589
		C2.4	0.1762	0.0555
		C2.5	0.1660	0.0522
Check consistency for C2.1, C2.2, C2.3, C2.4, and C2.5				
		CR		0.0602
C3	0.3064	C3.1	0.1354	0.0415
		C3.2	0.1673	0.0513
		C3.3	0.1284	0.0393
		C3.4	0.1673	0.0513
		C3.5	0.1587	0.0486
		C3.6	0.2429	0.0744
Check consistency for C3.1, C3.2, C3.3, C3.4, C3.5, and C3.6				
		CR		0.0905
Check consistency for the main criteria C1, C2, and C3				
CR = 0.0279				

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix B. Reclassified maps

Fig. B.1. Reclassified map illustrating suitability (1: least suitable, 9: highest suitability).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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